

www.arseam.com

HARDSHIP AND SUFFERING AND THEORY OF DIFFICULTY IN EXECUTION OF CONTRACT

Dr. Hussein Khodadai*

Phd of Private Law. , Iran
E-mail: hosein1.khodadady@gmail.com.

Dr.Majid Ghamami**

Associate Prof . Tehran University, Iran.
E-mail: mghamami@ut.ac.ir.

Abstract

The theory of difficulty in execution of contract (which deals with specific conditions created in the course of implementing the contract), as a new theory in the world of law, has some similarities to the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering (usr wa haraj), which is considered as a secondary rule governing primary rules. They are similar in terms of the application of the rule in the contracts and the results which are obtained from invoking the theory of difficulty and the implementation of hardship and suffering rule. First, because there is a same reason for invoking them that is implementation of the provisions of a forcible contract, a contract that its implementation is not impossible but it entails intolerable hardship for the engaged person, in a manner that it is possible to continue the commitment but it is injustice to persist on the enforcement of the contract, and in different cases in order to avoid injustice one can resort to the rule of the rejection of hardship and suffering or the theory of difficulty, and perform the contract in a different way. Second, because in both rules the affected person is given the right of adjustment or termination of the contract and conditions will be provided to get him free from the unjust and intolerable conditions. Then, we can say that although the rule of the rejection of hardship and suffering and the theory of difficulty are different in some aspects, they conform to each other in terms of the mentioned cases.

Key words: Theory of difficulty, The rule of hardship and suffering, Termination, Adjustment, Execution of the contract.

Introduction

The rule of hardship and suffering is one of the significant and fundamental jurisprudential rules which has an influential effect in the deduction of the rules. This rule, as one of the secondary rules, governs all primary rules and under the particular conditions it is applicable in all contracts including swap and non-swap.

Since the theory of difficulty of change supervises the economic aspects of the contracts and its goal is to make adjustments in economic conditions of contracts so that the time of the conclusion of the contract can be reestablished, it is invoked in only swap contracts.

Besides, in the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering If implementation of the provisions of the contract causes hardship

for the engaged person, due to the undue hardship which he is encountered he can resort to this rule, whether or not the contract is a continuous and long-term one, although the theory of difficulty of change is mostly applied in the continuous and long-term contracts. On the other hand, the result of implementation of the theory of difficulty is making adjustments in the economic conditions of the contract or providing the termination right to the affected party. But the result of executing the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering is mostly important and the possibility of the rescission of the contract and removing the hardship caused by it, not the right of unilateral modification and change of the conditions agreed upon over the contract.

Nevertheless, regardless of the mentioned differences, the theory of difficulty and the rule of the rejection of hardship and suffering are similar in one way or the other, in terms of the conditions of implementation and partly of objective that will be discussed in this paper.

A) The rule of hardship and suffering (Usr wa Haraj)

First: the meaning of 'Usr wa Haraj'

The word 'Haraj' literally means pressure, narrowness, guilt and forbidden thing (haram). It is said that haraj originally means community and a mass of objects so as to cause pressure and distress among those objects. (Isfahani 1412, Zeil vaje haraj-Abdolkareem, 1410,234). Likewise, it has been said that: "Al-haraj al-makan al-zeigh,

al-kathir al shajar, al-alam". (Abu Jeib,1408, Zeil vaje haraj).

Some have defined haraj the toughest difficulty. (Tabarsi,1410, 362:3).

In the holy Quran also the word 'haraj' means hardship and guilt, as God says:

“... مَا يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ لِيَجْعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ مِنْ حَرَجٍ وَلَكِنْ يُرِيدُ لِيُطَهِّرَكُمْ وَلِيُنِزِلَ عَلَيْكُمْ رِزْقًا غَيْرَ مَكْرُوهٍ...”

“...Allah does not intend to make difficulty for you, but He intends to purify you and complete His favor upon you that you may be grateful.

The word “Usr” is the opposite of “Yasr” and it means difficult, hard and tough times, in the holy Quran it has the same meaning, as God says: “Surely with every difficulty there is relief” or “God will grant, after hardship, ease”. Therefore, the meaning of ‘Usr’ is difficulty and hardship.

Second: categorization of hardship and difficulty

In respect of the degree and extend of hardship and difficulty jurists have made categorizations. Based on the cases which are considered as hardship and suffering (usr wa haraj), one of the jurists has classified hardship tasks into four, and out of these four he has found only one as a kind of usr wa haraj. The categorization is as follows:

1. Hardship and suffering to the extent that the engaged person cannot tolerate it.

2. Hardship and suffering which is less than the former case however, tolerating it will lead to the disturbance of the system.
3. Hardship and suffering that is less than the above two said-cases but it is to the extent that entails loss of life, money or honor.
4. The hardship which is tolerable and it doesn't lead to the disturbance of the system, but it is difficult to tolerate it.

In view of this jurist, the first category is not relevant to the present discussion and it should be dealt with in the book of principles which is related to license and transmutation "TAKLIFE MA LAYATAQ".

The second category is also not related to the present discussion, because the ugliness of the task which disturbs the system is too obvious to argue. As the aim of lawgiver is to preserve the system and it is not logical that he sets tasks which lead to disturbance in the system. The third category is taken as a harmless rule, and only the fourth category is a kind of *usr wa haraj* (hardship and suffering). (Makarem Shirazi, 170:1).

According to this categorization, it seems that one can say, if performing task is so hard and difficult that puts the involved person in tribulation and hardship, the rule would be applicable.

Third: documents of the rule of hardship and suffering

Book, traditions (Sunnah), wisdom and consensus are considered as the documentation of the rule. However, the two first documentations must be regarded as the only documentations of the rule. Because as an author has stated since in the categorizations, the rule of hardship and suffering does not include TAKLIF MALAYATALAGH and the task which causes disturbance in the system, and it only includes the cases in which performing the task is possible but it entails undue hardship hence, appeal to rational argument is not needed and consensus is not an independent reason (Mohammadi, 1373, 143) which we will talk about it later.

1-3 Book

One of the most important verses which is referred to as the proof of the rule of hardship and suffering is the verse 78 of Surah Haj. After obliging the believers to bow and prostrate and worship their God and to do good deeds, God in the next verse says, "وَجَاهِدُوا فِي اللَّهِ حَقَّ جِهَادِهِ هُوَ اجْتَبَاكُمْ وَمَا جَعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ" (Eliya, 1997, 143).

"And strive hard for the cause of God with all the striving that is due to Him, He has chosen you and has not laid upon you any hardship in religion...".

The meaning of strive in this verse includes *ISTELAHI* jihad and with regard to the preceding verse it also includes performing all necessary affairs and avoiding prohibited things. The word "religion" in the verse implies all rules and tasks not only the rule of Jihad.

In addition, the word "جَعَلَ" means that God has removed troublesome rules from the believers;

Similarly, مِنْ حَرَجٍ مَّا جَعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ refers to all Islamic rules rather restricted to specific rules, and the verse says that if the engaged person faces hardship and suffering in the wake of performing religious rules and obligations, these rules and obligations are removed from him.

One of the other verses which can be invoked for the rule of hardship and suffering is the verse six of surah Al-Maidah which is as follows:

وَإِنْ كُنْتُمْ مَرْضَىٰ أَوْ عَلَىٰ سَفَرٍ أَوْ جَاءَ أَحَدٌ مِنْكُمْ مِنَ الْغَائِطِ أَوْ لَامَسْتُمُ النِّسَاءَ فَلَمْ تَجِدُوا مَاءً فَتَيَمَّمُوا صَعِيدًا طَيِّبًا فَامْسَحُوا بِوُجُوهِكُمْ وَأَيْدِيكُمْ مِنْهُ مَا يُرِيدُ اللَّهُ لِيَجْعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ مِنْ حَرَجٍ وَلَكِنْ يُرِيدُ لِيُطَهِّرَكُمْ وَلِيُتِمَّ نِعْمَتَهُ عَلَيْكُمْ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَشْكُرُونَ

“And if you are in a state of janabah, then purify yourselves. But if you are ill or on a journey or one of you comes from the place of relieving himself or you have contacted women and do not find water, then seek clean earth and wipe over your faces and hands with it. Allah does not intend to make difficulty for you, but He intends to purify you and complete His favor upon you that you may be grateful”.

With respect to the previous verses, which are related to some non-devotional rules such as the rule of marriage with People of the Book and also with respect to the special emphasis given in the context of the verse and the way hardship is rejected, (Tabatabai, 230:5, 1420) it seems that rejection of hardship, came in the verse, covers the rules

which have appeared in this verse and in the beginning verses of Al-Maidah surah. In addition, on account of its generality and applicability it encompasses all Sharia laws and Islamic regulations.

2-3 traditions

There are a number of narrations quoted from infallible Imams which are taken as a basis for the rule of the rejection of hardship and suffering, in the following we explain them briefly:

The narration of Abdul Ala Mula Al Sam. “Gholta Le Abi abdellah alayha salam athrat fantagh zafari fajalta ala asbai marah fakafa asna belvozo? Ghala yarof haza va eshbaha men ketabal allah azza va ja: ghalal allah ma jaala alaykum fi diin men haraje amsah alayhe” (Ameli 1409, 327:1- Kalini, 11:1, 1429- Tusi, 1407, 103:1)

In this narration, the narrator is telling to Imam Sadegh that he fell down and his nail split and he has wrapped his finger, now how can he perform wuzu. Imam Sadegh (AS) says: the rule for this case and such like is taken from the book of God; because God has said that there is no hardship in your religion, then wipe over it. The following points are concluded from Imam’s answer:

1. Rejection of hardship is a general rule and according to Imam’s (AS) guidance it can be used to remove the rules which may cause hardship for the engaged persons.
2. Imam (AS) has invoked rejection of hardship in verse 78 of surah Hajj rather than rejection of hardship in wuzu vrse..- which matches better with the question-

therefore, it seems that LAHARAJ e MAZKUR in the last mentioned verse, besides being more general and inclusive than wuzu verse, it is also more related to the cases of common hardship than inherent hardship which has come in wuzu verse.

And narration from Abu Basir، “ عن ابى بصير، عن ابى عبد الله عليه السلام، قال: سألته عن الجنب يجعل الزكوة او التور فيدخل اصبعه فيه. قال ان كانت يده قدرة فليهرقه و ان كان لم يصبها قدر فليغتسل منه. هذا مما قال (Isfahani, 273:2, 1410). ”الله تعالى ما جعل عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ

Apparently, the question is about a person, in the state of Janabat, who has touched water in a container like jug or....with his finger and Imam (AS) has replied: if his hand was najis he should throw it away, but if any najis substance has not reached his hand, he can wash his body with that water, because this is one of the cases that God has said that He has not placed any hardship for you in religion.

there is an ambiguity in the given narration- since the cause of question is not clear- and also as it was said, it is mostly relevant to the Istehbabi rule of resistance from conventional contaminations rather than religious contamination, however these reasons don't contradict invoking it for rejection of hardship rules.

The other narration, MOVASAGHE Abi Basir، “ عن ابى بصير، قال، قلت لأبى عبد الله (ع) انا نساقر فرّما بلينا بالغدير من المطر يكون الى جانب القرية فيكون فيه العذرة و يبول فيه الصبى و تبول فيه الدابة و تروث. فقال (عليه السلام): ان عرض فى قلبك منه شىء فقل: هكذا، يعنى امزج الماء بيدك ثم توضع فانّ الدّين ليس

بمضيق؛ لانّ الله عزّ و جلّ يقول: ما جعل عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ (Ameli, 1409, 120:1).

Abi Basir asked Imam, in journeys we often reach lakes, near villages, which there are all kinds of najis things in them. Imam said, stir the water with your hand and then perform wudu (ablution) because there is no hardship in this matter. And God says:

”ما جعل عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ“

Therefore, there is indeed the reason of rejection of hardship and suffering and emergence of development and opening and removal of bottlenecks and straitened circumstances from muslims.

The famous Nabavi narration (Hadith-e-Nabavi) ”بعثت بالحنيفيّة السّهلة السّهلة“ (Maraqhi, 1417, 1: the section of rejection of hardship and suffering) means that, I was sent to easy religion of Hanif. If there were difficult and suffering rules in religion, it would have not been correct that the Prophet (pbhu) defines religion as an easy complex.

So, the mentioned narrations and some other narrations with the same theme, that we don't mention here to preserve briefness, explicitly or implicitly refer to the rejection of hardship and suffering as a general principle which is applicable to all fields of Islamic laws, and they are considered as incontrovertible legal basis for that principle.

3-3 Consensus

Since, according to Imam's belief, consensus will be considered as one of the

four reasons and equal book, tradition and wisdom as a basis for religious rules and it is authentic only when KASHEF AZ RAYE MASOM BASHAD. If the consensus of jurists is based on intellectual or narrative reason and they deduce a rule on that basis, that consensus would not be authentic and valid enough for others. The other jurists must examine the reason which has been the base of consensus, and deduce the religious rule from it because in such situations the understanding of each jurist is valid and authoritative only for himself not for others.

Thus, if in verifying the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering it is said that one of the jurisprudential bases has been the consensus of Islamic scholars on rebuttal of forging troublesome rule, it is not acceptable, because the reason of those who reach consensus is in fact the verses and narrations which we talked about. And also, because most scholars have not referred to this issue it is difficult to establish such a claim with certainty.

3-4 wisdom

Undoubtedly if hardship and suffering, as a result of doing a task is beyond one's tolerance or it leads to disturbance in the system of individual or social life, logically, such task is removed from the person. However, regarding the wisdom or rational basis of rejection of hardship and suffering, the hardship and suffering which is beyond a human's tolerance and leads to disturbance in the system of life is by no means the issue of debate, because as it was said, in this rule hardship and suffering means something which is bearable for human though, habitually it is hard to tolerate it and it puts

the engaged person in trouble and hardship. In verifying the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering (distress and constriction) - as a rational reason- generally two reasons are invoked, one is logical basis and the other the matter of grace.

Logical basis, some believe that the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering is an intellectual principle and logic basis supports it. They argue that doing a task which would cause undue hardship is logically impossible; because the reason for the task is obedience and subjection and it would be violated by performing a task beyond one's tolerance. (Qazvini, 1418, without page number).

Besides, most people do the tasks because they are afraid of God's punishment and if there was no fear they would not adhere to the rules and disobey and rebel against God because most people do not seek the satisfaction of the holy legislator. So, if they are engaged to do difficult tasks they refuse and then they fall into sin and God's wrath will remain on them. It is wisely that tasks which entail public rebellion would be considered obscene. (Tabrizi, 1369, without page number)

On the contrary, some believe that logic basis in this case and it cannot be invoked. Some other scholars have also said that implementation of the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering in cases which don't lead to disturbance in life's system is questionable, because it's a non-verbal principle. (Ansari, 1412, 196:1) and even some have attributed this theory to MASHHORE FOGHAHA, (Ashtiyani, 1403, without page number). However,

since most scholars have not taken the rejection of hardship and suffering as an independent rule of jurisprudent, therefore it is not acceptable to attribute this theory to MASHHORE FOGHAHA).

According to the rational rule and logical basis of rejection of hardship and suffering, maybe it is argued that in case of a logical issue the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering must be a definite and non-allocable principle, while there are many other tasks in Sharia law such as the obligation to defend (Jihad) and paying off compensation and retaliations which performing them entails hardship and difficulty.

To reject this argumentation we can say that they are not troublesome and also- even if they are proved to do so- the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering is applied only for the rules that in certain situations they will cause hardship not like the rules such as jihad and Hajj that are permanently and in nature are associated with hardship. Such rules are excluded from this principle, therefore they don't negate the logical basis for the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering.

The rule of grace

Some have invoked the rule of kindness to prove the rationality of the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering and they say that, doing a task which leads to undue hardship provokes sin and it is against kindness; because in most cases the intention behind doing a task is obedience

and subordination and it would be violated if performing the task is beyond tolerance. (Qazwini, 1418, without page number). On the other hand, since all the engaged persons don't seek God's consent and they perform the duties out of fear of punishment therefore, if they are bound to perform a difficult task, they would avoid it and commit sin and shall deserve anger and wrath of legislator. Acceptance of such rules is not in accordance with God's grace because it gets people away from Him. (Tabrizi, 1369, without page number).

In adducing this theory, it is said that if a task leads to lots of objections by the engaged persons it doesn't mean that it is against the grace but the violations are due to the defects in the engaged persons not in the rules and laws. Because if the objections lead to avoiding and removing the task then there shall be no task, because most of the engaged people may disagree with some tasks and also the foundation of this theory is that the grace entails removal of task because the existence of task causes objection by the engaged person.

In response to this controversy it is said that, there is a difference between the situations in which the engaged person avoids doing the task due to his own defect and the cases in which the difficulty of the task makes him to do so.

If the engaged person is indifferent towards the duties, it doesn't mean that the duties should be removed as a matter of grace. However, if the religious law makes the engaged person not to perform the duties

and leads him to fall into sin, it is against the grace, this include troublesome duties.

In addition, it is not correct to assume that removal of task is a prerequisite to grace, because the issue of obedience and objection is fulfilled by addressing.

Hence, there should be a task so that those who obey and those who object are rewarded according to what they do by their choice against the task, and this would not negate the grace. However, in tasks leading to hardship, the task in itself causes complain and objection and it is the nature of task which leads to sin which its issue by grand legislator who is wise is impossible. (Maraghi, 1417,1: the section of rejection of hardship and suffering)

Fourth: substances of the rule of hardship and suffering

There are different beliefs among scholars about whether the substances in the argumentation of the rejection of rules are virtual or real, or LESSANE NAFYE MOZO, or in fact it means negation. Since the most argumentations by scholars has been about the substances of LAZARAR principle, a detailed discussion which is beyond the scope of this paper, the detailed explanation of different theories and their reasoning bases are avoided here and I give only a digest of the theory of Sheikh Ansari and his eminent student Mohaghegh Khorasani.

1-4 negation of the rule

In discussing about the substance of LAZARAR principle and the concept of LAZARAR, Shiekh Ansari believes that it

means non-legislation of hardship leading rule. In other words, the rule which entails harm for the engaged persons has not been legislated by the legislator, whether it is TAKLIFI (as a duty) or Vazi (imposed). (Ansari, 1412, 526:1). In other places, discussing about several theories about the principle of LAZARAR and explaining the saying, these scholars state that “La Zarar va la zaraar fil Islam” implies rejection of the religious law which will cause harm for the servants. On the other hand, there is no MAJOLE ZARAR in Islam which performing it causes harm for the servants. (Ansari, 1424, 372:5).

According to them, the substance of the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering is- as the principle of LAZARAR-rejection of troublesome rule in the religion; that is there is no troublesome rule legalized in Islam which puts the engaged people in trouble and difficulty.

2-4 Rejection of effect

According to the theory of Mohaghegh Khorasani, with reason of rejection of hardship, the claim of real rejection has become the subject of HARAJI, therefore, the rule associated with it will also be rejected. That’s why this theory is called “Nafye hokm be lessane nafye mozo”.

Similarly, in narrations such as “La Shakal Kasir al-Shak” and “La Baiy Ella fil Molk” or “ La Rahn ELLs Maghbozan” instead of directly rejecting the rule which governs cases such as doubt, sale and mortgage, its topic is rejected as a claim, and the rejection of the rule which is its result is indirectly inferred. (Akhond Khorasani, 1419, 381:2).

This theory has been criticized in some ways; for instance in the verse “*مَا جَعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ*” “*فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ*”, which is one of the proofs of the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering, religion, in other words religious tasks and laws is subject of rejection, and it in fact means “*لَمْ يَجْعَلْ فِي الاحكام حكما حرجيا*”. So, from the beginning, religion, and not the topic of rules, has been the subject of rejection so that there would be an opportunity for (Naeeni, 1374, 96:3).

3-4 Sultan prohibition

According to some other scholars, the substance of the reason of LAZARAR and rejection of hardship is sultan or government prohibition. Based on this theory, some rules such as LAZARAR and LA HARAJ emanate from the position of monarchy and government of the holy prophet of Islam and they have been issued for running the society and government, in other words, its substance is government and sultan prohibition not religious prohibition.

According to this theory, when the religious reason begins with the words “Qaza” or “Amr” or “Hokm” the rule therein is in fact a kind of government rules. (Musavi Khomeini, 1418, 50:1). This theory is not accepted at least about the proofs of rejection of hardship, because it seems that “*مَا جَعَلَ عَلَيْكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ مِنْ حَرَجٍ*” has emergence in rejection as its true meaning; unless we consider the foundation of the principle of hardship and suffering as HADISE LAZARAR.

However, it is important to mention that there is a set of rules which are within the human’s control and he is free to take advantage or discard the benefits which are the outcome of such rules. The purpose of establishing such rules is not to impose obligations on humans and to force them to perform them in all situations, but they are to develop and facilitate individual and society’s affairs. This group of rules are called Tarkhisi laws or in short “Rokhsat”.

There is another set of rules which are tied to the legislator’s will with consideration of benefits such as public order. The bounds of such rules should be respected at all times and under any circumstances or pretexts they cannot be avoided. This set of rules are imperative rules. In other words, those rules are called imperative and mandatory which observing them is compulsory and we can’t disagree them and they are called “Azimat”.

Now, the question is whether the rule of hardship and suffering is from the first or second set?

It sounds that in non-worship affairs, the principle of hardship and suffering is a Rokhsat type; because the substance of this principle is in fact a kind of Tarkhis for the person who is qualified so, so that if he likes, he would be able to use his right by resorting to this religious and legal Rokhsat (permission) and get himself free from the undue hardship which he has encountered, otherwise by refusing this right he tolerates the hardship. In other words, this principle removes the necessity of bearing the hardship by the person, though it doesn’t

mean that with the intention of tolerating the hardship, he can not avoid practicing it. Hence, it is obvious that the cases in which some actions and measurements in personal properties cause hardship for the adjacent owners, until the affected owner has protested and complained about this issue in court, he cannot revoke the effects of occupation and remove troublesome affairs only due to the hardship of possessive occupation by the said person.

In answering the above question, there is a discrepancy between beliefs about worships. Some take this principle as an instance of Tarkhisi rules and therefore, they know the worships acceptable, while some others believe that the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering is a kind of Azimat and performing hardship and harm worships is void, and another group with a more detailed view, consider the hardship (HARAJI) rules and suffering rules acceptable and void respectively.

Those who believe that the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering is a Tarkhisi rule and therefore believe in acceptability of hardship and suffering worships argue that the reason and support of the principle of LAHARAJ AND LAZARAR is gratefulness and if the worships that the engaged persons have performed are not acceptable without applying the rule of rejection of hardship, the engaged person is required to suffer undue hardship and this is against the goal of legislator for setting the rule of rejection of hardship. Thereupon, if a person who because of hardship for him in doing Wudhu has to perform Tayamum, with discarding

the implementation of the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering he performs wudhu and we consider that wudhu void because of treating the rule of rejection of hardship as Azimat, the engaged person will be in trouble of repeating the duty that this is incompatible with the goal of setting this rule.

Those who find the rule of rejection of hardship as Azimat- and also believe in the invalidity of HARAJI and ZARARI worships – believe that on account of the principle of rejection of hardship and because of governance of the proofs of this principle over the first proofs the rules, AHKAME MOSOF BE HARAJ AZ ARSEYE TASHRII VA JAAL NAFY SHODE, FARDE HARAJI will be excluded from the other proofs of worships. In other words, TAKHSIS BE LESANE HOKOMAT, implies that (troublesome rule doesn't have criteria and order and appropriateness therefore, performing the worships without existence of criteria and with intention of worship is considered a kind of legislation which there is no doubt in its respectability. In addition, if troublesome worship is acceptable, there would be EJTEME NAGHZEIN, it means that for example in troublesome wudhu the legislator's verdict is that if there is water, one has to perform wudhu otherwise he should perform Tayamum. This explanation illustrates that the obligatory duty is one of the two. So, we can't say that in case of hardship one can either perform wudhu or Tayamum; because in case of choice by the person, EJTEME NAGHZEIN would come up. Then about the process of rule , inevitably we have to say that the

troublesome worship is void. (Naeeni, 1373, 216:2). Those with more detailed view- who believe in corruption in Zarari worship and acceptability of troublesome worship- in fact consider Zarari worship void because of prohibition of self-harm - which is Haram and MOBAAD- because basically inhibition in worships may lead to corruption- they don't take Lazarar principle as an instance of Azimat. In the other part of this detailed view, which is about the acceptability of troublesome worships, they are in agreement with the first group, and they know the rule of rejection of hardship as evidence of Tarkhisi rules, that's why to confirm the theory of the first group they say that the governance of the proofs of LA Haraj over the primary proofs don't abolish the criteria, appropriateness and command of worship, so as to performing the task without practicing the rule of rejection of hardship is considered legislation (Tashrii) and be Haram, but the governance of La HARAJ obviates only the necessity and obligation of the primary rule though it does indicate the criteria and the person can, with the purpose of criteria, perform the worship with the intention of closeness (Taqarob). (Hamedani, 1416, 463). Additionally, the reason of rejection of hardship obviates only ELZAMI rules, because ELZAMI rule will put the engaged person in problem while in Tarkhsi rules since TARKHIS (permission) will not cause hardship for the engaged person, the reason of rejection of hardship won't be applied. (Mohaghegh Damad Yazdi, 1406,2: 80-100).

B) The theory of difficulty

First: the concept of the theory of difficulty

The theory of difficulty is one of the most complex themes in the issues of the rights of contracts. Some writers believe that the reason of this complexity is on one hand related to its nature as a relative concept and it varies from one case to another and on the other hand it is because of strict viewpoints that some traditional schools of thought have adopted to identify it as a way to terminate or modify the contracts. (Ahmadpour, 2005,4).

Maybe it's because of this complexity that some writers have enclosed the difficulty of performing the commitment to the impossibility of performing the contract. According to these writers, there are two types of non-performance:

- 1- Absolute non-performance
- 2- Practical non-performance or becoming impractical

In the first condition, the performance has become impossible in financial or legal terms, therefore under no circumstances the committed person will be able to perform it. In the second condition, performing the contract will not become impossible absolutely, but due to new situations it will just become more difficult and costly. Therefore, the impracticality is a means of exemption. (Jowit, 1977, 942)

It looks as if this analysis has come up against serious problems, since the impossibility and difficulty of performing the commitment are significantly different.

In stating these differences and criticizing this theory, a writer has attended to three main differences which seem to be correct. They are:

1. The difficulty of performing the contract is subject to change in non-inherent conditions of contract or loss of its secondary provision (the necessity of contractual adjustment), while, the impossibility of performance is because of inherent conditions of contract and change of its basic nature.

2. The instability which is created in the contract, due to difficulty in performing the commitment, may have nothing to do with the contract, in other words, it is not attributed to the true will of the parties. However, the instability which is created because of impossibility of performing the contract and leads to dissolution arises from the intention of parties.

3. The result of the difficulty of adjustment and in case of the impossibility of adjustment, termination will be the right of the party who suffers losses because of change in circumstances. But, the result of impossibility is giving the right of termination to either of parties. (Shafaii, 1376,58).

However, despite the complexity of the issue and emergence of the recent matters, legal writers and international institutions have brought up a definition of difficulty in performing the contract. Indeed, the theory of change in conditions and circumstances, as an exception of the principle of necessity in contracts or “Isalat lozom”, entitles the affected person by the unexpected event to

be exempted from the principle of necessity to fulfil the commitment, and by fair adjustment or dissolution of contract remove or lessen the unintended and unexpected loss. (Mohaghegh damad Yazdi, 108:2, 1406).

Some believe that the legal foundation of this theory is that the parties of the contract have concluded it on this stipulation that they adhere to it so long as the conditions and circumstances and the financial balance at the time of conclusion of the contract do not change. And in case of any unexpected event and change in the circumstances, the affected party has right to void the contract.

Some other believe that, removal of the unintended loss resulting from the appearance of sudden and unexpected events is the permit for decadence of the necessity of fulfilling the contract and turning the principle of necessity of contracts to the permit which due to it the loss which is suffered by the affected person is removed by termination or adjustment of the contract. However, this theory is in fact to deal with the adverse conditions resulting from the occurrence of unexpected events and to justify the possibility of not fulfilling the commitment in financial and MOSTAMARI contracts which has been subject to changes in unfair and excruciating economic balance against one of the parties. (Mohaghegh Damad Yazdi, 1406, 108:2).

Second: the conditions of applying the theory of difficulty

The first condition is occurrence of an incident or crisis. The incident or exigency must have the following conditions:

First: it must be unexpected, that is to say that at the time of drawing up the contract the parties of contract by no means predict its occurrence in future and also don't expect it.

Second: it must be unavoidable and not by the will of the parties, that is, the person affected by the occurrence of the incident must not be able to repel it, in other words its happening must be inevitable.

Third: the incident or crisis leads to public and inclusive changes and affects all people not just changes the conditions for the parties of the contract.

The second condition is that the unexpected incident must result in drastic changes in conditions of the contract, so that it affects the primary mutual consent and fundamental elements of the consensus such as AVAZEINE MOAMELEH.

Third condition, terms and conditions of the subjects which are being committed in the course of the contract must change in a way that according to common law, ETLAGHE SALB or lack of balance between AVAZEIN will be possible in a non-negligible and bearable manner.

Fourth condition which is very important, implementation of the substance of the contract becomes difficult so that continuing the contractual relationship is cumbersome for the affected party.

And finally the fifth condition is that, the contract is settled on this fundamental assumption that in the course of creating and

implementing the provisions of the contract incidents which lead to drastic changes in conditions do not happen, because by virtue of this theory the parties of contract presumed that according to their conventional prediction, no detrimental event occurs while creating and implementing provisions of contract, and if it occurs the affected person is entitled to avoid fulfilling his commitment.

By looking attentively in this context and considering the definition and conditions of invoking "Force Majeure" we can see that there are significant differences between these two conditions which distinguish them from each other and specifies the applicability of each one of them.

One of these fundamental differences is that, Force Majeure destroys the possibility of implementation and continuation of contractual relationships while, the theory of change in conditions causes hardship in implementing the provisions of contract. Another difference is that, in the theory of difficulty the changes and alterations which have happened will entail adjustment- and in some particular occasions- exemption of the engaged person from performing his commitment, but Force Majeure is the cause of exemption of the affected person from performing the commitment and consequently it leads to termination of contractual relationship.

Third: comparing the rule of hardship and suffering to the theory of difficulty

In the previous discussions principle and theory of difficulty was defined.

Some of the legal writers have given positive answer to this question while some other have rejected such a comparison. In this section to clarify the issue and get conclusions, the stated comments will be examined.

Before entering into the main discussion, it is essential to refer to this point that by comparing the hardship and suffering to the theory of difficulty, some writers have pointed some differences between these two. For example, the principle of rejection of hardship and suffering is applied for all contracts including swap and non-swap as well as also continues and non-continues while the theory of difficulty is only applied to swap and continues contracts (Mohaghegh Damad Yazdi, 1406, 93:2). This theory seems correct however, we should bear in mind that by bringing forth this rule in this article we don't mean that the theory of difficulty is exactly the same as the principle of hardship and suffering in the laws of Iran based on Islamic jurisprudence.

Because it is obvious that the principle of hardship and suffering as a general principle is broader than theories such as the theory of difficulty. But the purpose is to compare the theory of difficulty to the principle of hardship and suffering.

Some of the legal writers believe that, in response to the raised question, based on the principles and rules accepted by the jurists, we should say that if the unexpected events lead to the impossibility of implementation of contract, under the rational rule GHOBHE TAKLIFE MA LA YATAGH termination of contract is incontrovertible.

In all other conditions also according to ETLAGH and absence of proofs for rejection of hardship and suffering, positive reply is stronger. In support of this view some jurists like Hanafi jurists are cited, who have found the unforeseen incidents effective in termination, in cases which they cause difficulty in executing the contract. The given example, is the cases in which in village and people of village leave the place or the landlord owes a third person and he doesn't have anything else than the rent price of the place which has given on rent or the tenant becomes indigent and he can't keep working in the place he is renting. Nevertheless, according to these writers, revision in transaction is not in accordance with Islamic principle such as the condition of compromise for authenticity of transactions. And they know termination of transaction fairer and more equitable. (Musavi, Kanon vokala website).

Some others have given negative reply to this question and they argue that even if the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering can lead to adjustment or termination of a contract, because of difficulty in performing it, and if this analysis is in consistent with legal principles, but in cases which hardship and suffering can be removed or compensated by executing the primary rule of contract there is no need to perform the secondary rule. (Shafae, 1376, 166).

In fact, according to this writer, the true basis of the primary rule of contract is establishment of a kind of compromise or conventions and when it is possible to remove the hardship and suffering by relying on the implied condition, resorting to the rule is not needed.

In addition to these argumentations there is a third view which besides accepting the practice of the rule of hardship and suffering, in such cases with stating some reasons and likely objections has somehow accepted the possibility of adjustment in contract by invoking this rule. In this view, it is argued that since the rule of hardship and suffering is not limited to task rules (AHKAME TAAKLIFI) and if imposed rule (VAZI) also leads to undue hardship it nullifies the rule. And also in long term contracts that in the course of performing the contract some unforeseen incidents lead to hardship of performing the contract one can basically invoke the rule of hardship and suffering. (Bigdeli, 1384, 192).

Objections are as follow:

First: the rule of hardship and suffering has no demonstrative effect and its only effect is removing troublesome rule. Thus, on the assumption that all conditions for invoking the rule exist, the rule can only nullify the necessity. Therefore, adjustment of contract by judge requires another reason and the rule of rejection of hardship and suffering cannot support or confirm it. Second, acceptance of termination as the result of the rule of hardship and suffering is in contradiction with what we are looking for in theories about changes in conditions and difficulty in executing the contract. On the other hand, in most cases, termination of contracts by the engaged person will put the other party in loss or trouble, thus, termination also has no practical effect. (Bigdeli, 1384, 192).

However, in response to objections, by bringing up two introductions, some results, different from the results of the first theory, were obtained which we will elaborate them here. These two introductions include, first, the rule of hardship and suffering is meant for removing cumbersome duties and the primary reason is not interfering in the rules, hence if performing the tasks or duties becomes difficult, the task is removed only until the difficulty exists, without talking about removing the main task. Second, so long as there is any possibility to remove the hardship, the rule would not be applied. The result which is gained from this introduction is that, if fulfillment of the commitment becomes troublesome for either of the parties, from the religious point of view, only removing hardship from that person would be possible; but his commitment will not change or he won't be entitled to adjust or terminate, and during the time that there wasn't any hardship he must perform it. And in situations which there isn't such opportunity, for example between the time of performing and the commitment, there should be desired unity. From the beginning we cannot consider removal of the rule of necessity as the result of hardship and suffering, but as the obligee accepts the change in conditions, there would be no foundation for changing the rule of contract. Thus, the engaged person must try and give suggestions for removing the undue hardship from the engaged person in the course of implementing the commitment, and even if in spite of the parties efforts, performing the commitment without hardship is not possible, according to the

rule, there is no way except removing the necessity of contract and its termination.

Otherwise, if the delay makes the performance fruitless for the obligee or the obligee is not consent with it, since according to LAHARAJ, bearing the pressure on the engaged person is not possible, the enacted rule of necessity is removed. If the engaged person gives suggestions for taking the undue hardship away, termination is not acceptable. (197, 198-1384).

As we can see, according to this view, termination of contract is acceptable only if taking hardship away is not possible and the obligee does not cooperate. It seems that among the proposed views, third view must be confirmed, because based on the given argumentations, in addition to be in consistent with principles and conditions of executing the theory of difficulty, this theory is also in consistent with relevant modern needs of international community.

Conclusion

By looking at the issues which were discussed in the last chapter it seems that this rule is compatible with the theory of difficulty and based on the view of a writer, it is verifiable in many ways as follow:

First: if the rule of hardship and suffering can obviate troublesome rules between God and His servants, which have a kind of sanctity, it must definitely be able to remove hardship in private contracts. (Keshvari, 1374, 129)

Second: this rule is also compatible with the principle of necessity in contracts. Because if the hardship can be removed from the

engaged person by the suggestions of the obligee, the possibility of termination would also be canceled.

Third: since besides rejection of interference, judge openly leads the contract toward adjustment, needs of the day are taken into consideration.

Because although according to new conditions and difficulty in performing the contract judge has no right to do adjustment, the proposed solutions are practically for adjustment, and such adjustment does not conflict with our principles.

Fourth: as this writer has pointed out, this basis also leads to coherence and coordination in the legislative system of country. Because if we take hardship and suffering as the basis of adjustment, all laws that exist in this area will become coordinated. (Bigdeli, 1384, 198-199).

Fifth: since the jurists and lawyers basically prefer to invoke common and current foundations rather than invoke new rules and foundations to justify new theories, and also because the rule of hardship and suffering is one of the known and definite rules which is supported by strong legal foundations therefore resorting to such theories as the theory of difficulty with such strong legal foundations is more reasonable and acceptable. And finally since the rule of hardship and suffering as a general rule in the laws of Iran can cover many other foundations, it has precedence over the other two foundations.

منابع و ماخذ

منابع فارسی:

1. بیگدلی، سعید، (1384) **تعدیل قرارداد**، چ 1، میزان، تهران.
2. شفایی، محمدرضا، (1376) **بررسی تطبیقی نظریه تغییر اوضاع و احوال در قراردادها**، چ 1، ققنوس، تهران.
3. کشوری، عیسی، (1374) **کاربرد قواعد فقه در حقوق**، نشر غیاث، تهران.
4. محقق داماد یزدی، مصطفی، (1379) **قواعد فقه**، (بخش مدنی 2) سمت، چ 1، تهران.
5. محمدی، ابوالحسن، (1373) **قواعد فقه**، چ 1، یلدا، تهران، تهران.
6. موسوی، ابراهیم، **قاعده نفی عسرو حرج**، سایت کانون وکلا.

منابع عربی:

1. اخوند خراسانی، (1419) **کفایه الاصول**، موسسه آل البيت، قم.
2. آشتیانی، میرزا محمد حسن بن جعفر، (1403) **القواعد الفقیهه (بحر الفوائد)**، جلد دوم، انتشارات کتابخانه آیه الله مرعشی نجفی، چاپ اول، قم.
3. اصفهانی، حسین بن محمد راغب، (1412) **مفردات الفاظ القرآن**، دارالعلم، چاپ اول، لبنان.
4. اصفهانی، مجلسی دوم، محمداقصر بن محمد تقی، (1410) **بحار الانوار الجامعه لدرر اخبار الائمه الاطهار علیهم السلام**، موسسه الطبع و النشر، چاپ اول، بیروت.
5. انصاری، شیخ مرتضی، (1424) **المکاسب**، الجزء الخامس، الطبعة الخامسة، المطبعة الشریعة، قم.
6. انصاری، مرتضی، (1412) **فراند الاصول**، دارالعلم، قم.
7. تبریزی، موسی بن جعفر بن احمد، (1369) **اوثق الوسائل**، کتابفروشی کتبی نجفی، چاپ اول، قم.
8. سعدی، ابوجیب، (1408) **قاموس المحيط**، دار الفکر، چاپ دوم، دمشق.
9. عاملی، حر، محمد بن حسن، (1409) **تفصیل وسائل الشیعه الی تحصیل مسائل الشریعه**، موسسه آل البيت (ع)، چاپ اول، قم.
10. عبدالکریم، عبدالرحیم بن، (1410) **منتهی العرب فی لغة العرب**، جلد 1، الدار الشامی، چاپ اول، لبنان.
11. طباطبایی، سید محمدحسین، (1420) **المیزان فی تفسیر القرآن**، جلد 5، دارالعلم، قم.
12. طبرسی، فضل بن حسن، (1410) **مجمع البیان**، جلد 3، مجمع البحوث الاسلامیه، چاپ اول، مشهد.
13. طوسی، ابوجعفر، محمد بن حسن، (1407) **تهذیب الاحکام**، دارالکتب الاسلامیه، چاپ چهارم، تهران.
14. کلینی، محمد بن یعقوب، (1429) **الکافی**، دارالحديث للطباعة والنشر، چاپ اول، قم.
15. قزوینی، ابراهیم، (1418) **ضوابط الاصول**، نشر مرصاد، قم.
16. مراغی، سیدمیر عبدالفتاح بن حسینی، (1417) **العناوین الفقیهه**، جلد اول، دفتر انتشارات اسلامی وابسته به جامعه مدرسین حوزه عملیه قم، چاپ اول، قم.
17. مکارم شیرازی، ناصر، **القواعد الفقیهه**، الجزء الاول، طبعه الاول، مدرسة الامام علی بن ابی طالب، قم.
18. نایینی، میرزا محمدحسین غروی، (1374) **فوائد الاصول**، المكتبة المحمدیه، چاپ اول، تهران، 1374.
19. نایینی، میرزا محمدحسین غروی، (1373) **منیه الطالب فی حاشیه المکاسب**، المكتبة المحمدیه، چاپ اول، تهران.
20. موسوی خمینی، سید روح الله، (1418) **الرسائل**، موسسه تنظیم و نشر آثار امام خمینی، چاپ اول، تهران.
21. همدانی، آقارضا بن محمد هادی، (1416) **مصباح الفقیهه**، موسسه الجعفریه لاحیاء التراث و موسسه النشر الاسلامی، چاپ اول، قم.

منابع لاتین:

1. Ahmadpour, Ayoub, (2005) **Economic Hardship in Performance of Contract: A Comparative Study of English, American and German Law and CISG, the UNIDROIT Principle and PECL** Aberdeen. Maxwell, London
3. Jowit, Earl, (1977) **The Dictionary of English Law**, 2th ed, by John Bark, vol1, Sweet